

ISSN-0975-5535

The Horizon

A Journal of Social Sciences

No. II/2010, Volume-I

July 2010

Towards light

Chief Editor: B S Yadav

ATTITUDE TOWARDS PRIVATE LABELS AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF CONSUMER SENSORY EVALUATION OF PACKAGED FOOD IN NCR, INDIA

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INTRODUCTION

In the post liberalization era, the retail industry in India is experiencing an unprecedented boom. Recently, India witnessed a lot of dynamism in this industry in terms of retail formats, structure, players, regulations etc. Traditionally, the Indian retail industry was dominated by unorganized local players, with consumers shopping at mom-and-pop operations, roadside markets, and small grocery stores for their daily needs. While an estimated 85 percent of retail outlets continue to operate in these traditional formats, the last few years has seen a rise in modern retail formats such as hypermarkets, department stores, multi-storied malls, and specialty stores—particularly in metros and large cities. Indian corporate behemoths like Reliance, Tata, RPG, Future Group, Bharti Group, K Raheja Corp. etc are looking to tap into the growing potential of the organized retail market. They are slowly expanding their retail operations with a number of innovative experiments and strategies. International retailers are also keenly watching the Indian Government's policies, which presently only allow foreign retailers limited entry-either through franchising deals with local partners or joint venture partnerships with Indian companies.

Most of these retailers are offering Private label brand (also referred to as store brand or distributors' or retailers' brand) which is defined by American Marketing Association as "a brand name or label name attached to or used in the marketing of a product other than by the product manufacture; usually by a retailer" as an alternative to national and international brands. By doing so, retailers are moving from a position of being solely a distribution channel member to become direct competitors to the manufacturers. Viewed in another way, the retailers are transforming themselves from pure customers to the manufacturers of national brands to direct competitors to the manufactures (Dhar and Hoch, 1997).

Most of organized retail players carry processed packaged food as one of the category. A food product is defined as an aggregation of attributes at different levels. According to Grunert et al. (2000) these are: search attributes (e.g. price, colour), experience attributes (e.g. taste and flavour) and credence attributes (e.g. health and safety). These attributes are considered as evaluative criteria in consumer's purchase decisions and are transposed to consumer perception through a process of interaction of product characteristics and personal socio-demographic, economic, psychographic, behavioural and cognitive determinants (Mowen, 1993). Food selection and consumption is therefore a complex phenomenon influenced by a multitude of factors.

Individual socio-demographic and economic characteristics are commonly included when consumers are making a purchasing decision and they have to form quality expectations based on quality cues (Tuorila et al., 1998). Consumers form their quality expectation for most of the food categories on extrinsic cues such as price, brand name, brand familiarity, advertisements, store characteristics etc. as intrinsic cues such as taste; flavor etc can not be evaluated in packaged food products. The effects of extrinsic cues on consumer behaviour and its effect on consumer expectations have been widely studied (for a review see Deliza and MacFie, 1996). Price has been considered as a very important cue and received a great part of the research attention. However, in the literature (Jacoby et al., 1971) the theory that price is an objective cue, contrary to other factors being defined as subjective was established. In addition, for the regularity of brand's usage the most frequently read information about the foodstuff selected is important (Chernatony, 1991). Keller (2002) identified the following key functions of the brand for consumers: identification of origin; definition of responsibility of producer; risk reduction; search cost reduction and a virtual contract with producer (promise, guarantee). While Deliza and MacFie (1996) put the main focus of brand on informational cue. Consumers combine actual information from shopping environment with past experiences and use them to make purchase decision, but they strive for a "cognitive efficiency" and try to use minimum of information. As a result, they use a brand as a simplifier of a decision making process and hence the foundation of brand power.

There is clear evidence from research work that non-sensory attributes of food (extrinsic cues) affect the sensory acceptability of a food product (Di Monaco et al., 2003). However, external attributes mainly affect purchase decision, while sensory attributes confirm liking of a product and therefore determine repeat purchase and loyalty. Rather large research attention has been devoted to the effect of brand on overall liking and sensory evaluation of food (Deliza and MacFie, 1996).

It has been pointed out that the effect of a brand in the food choice is also largely dependant on individual characteristics of consumers and it is possible to distinguish them regarding to their sensitivity to brand. The effect of brand on consumer is well represented in scientific literature, however there are much less studies regarding the private labels. DelVecchio (2001) prepared a research focusing on the role of product category characteristics on private label perception and acceptability. He found that the consumer perception and penetration success of private label is driven by the segment complexity, quality variance, price and inter-purchase time. The private label shopper has been identified as price sensitive but not promotion sensitive (Baltas, 1997). High importance has been found regarding the familiarity with the product. Guerrero et al. (2000) have studied consumer attitude towards private labels in Spain. They founded that the Spanish consumers perceive private label products as reliable, different from producer brands and are good value for money.

The objective of the present study is to extend the research area focusing on the direct comparison of private label, manufacturer label and local generic label. The main objective is to examine to which extent an extrinsic factor (information on

brand) affects hedonic sensory judgment and whether there is a difference in respect to the type of brand.

The research focuses on food consumers in NCR in India. The organized retailers have successfully acquired the strategy of private label and introduced packaged food products giving direct competition to national brands. In the beginning these retailers introduced private label products as a mechanism to increase profitability as these provide higher margins. But in later phases these packaged food items also serve other motives like store image building, increasing customer loyalty etc of the retailers.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in two consecutive stages. First, two focus groups were formed with 6 participants in each, discussing food purchasing behavior with special attention to private label food products. These focus groups were composed of eight females and four males of different age groups. At the final stage of each focus group a preliminary consumer sensory evaluation test was performed. The latter was intended to determine the consumer sensory evaluation of food products. Potato chips were selected to serve as a research object since they offer a rather limited possibility for product differentiation. Furthermore, potato chips are widely available and used in India and these were among the first sold packaged food product under private label.

Wording of consumers relating to the private labels were carefully studied from the focus groups discussions and used while preparing the questionnaire as suggested by Malholtra (2007).

The second part of the research was a consumer study in two sessions with an attitude questionnaire containing socio demography, purchase behavior and sensory evaluation test involving 118 participants. Non probability convenience sampling was used.

Table 1 : Basic Demographic Detail of the Sample

Age group	Gender		Total %
	Male %	Female %	
Less than 20	7.6	11.9	19.5
20-30	8.5	11.0	19.5
30-40	13.6	12.7	26.3
above 40	16.1	18.6	34.7
Total	45.8	54.2	100.0
Minimum	Maximum	Average	Std. Deviation
17	61	41.37	12.44

Survey was conducted in two shopping malls in NCR, India on two consecutive Sundays to ensure homogeneity of the population. The experiments were done in purposely prepared sites with minimally required conditions for consumer sensory evaluations. The participants were asked to fill the questionnaire and to express their opinion about three samples of potato chips on a ten-point hedonic scale. For the purposes of this experiment it was sufficient to ask consumers for simple judgment on general acceptability (level of likeness) of the product without indicating specific sensory characteristic. It is believed that consumers make hedonic judgment considering the product as a whole and are generally not able to concentrate on singular sensory characteristics.

Three brands of potato chips one national label, one private label and one local generic label widely available in Indian market were included. In the first session on the first Sunday samples were served in neutral plastic containers labeled with a random alphabetical code - so called "blind testing". In the second session on next Sunday participants were served from the original packaging of potato chips and hence they were informed about the brand ("informed testing"). After both the testing sessions consumers completed the questionnaire.

Table 2 : Experimental Design

Experimental Conditions	No. of Subjects	Identification of Samples
Blind	60	Alphabetical Code
Informed	58	Brand Name

Results from the consumer questionnaire were processed using general descriptive statistical methods. In order to evaluate the effect of the testing conditions on the hedonic ratings of potato chips the difference between informed and blind ratings was calculated (I-B). Independent - Samples t-test was used to evaluate the statistical significance of the rating difference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the consumer questionnaire mainly confirmed the evident trend of increasing private label market share in the region. As much as 44.9 % of the respondents were classified into the "regular buyer" category of private labels. 28 % were classified in "frequent buyer" category and only 23.7% in "occasional buyer" category. Only 3.4% cases were reported in rare buyer and never buy category.

Table 3 : Store Brand Purchase Frequency

Purchase Behavior	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Regularly	53	44.9	43.2
Frequently	33	28.0	70.3
Occasionally	28	23.7	96.6
Rarely	4	3.4	100.0
Total	118	100.0	

Table below shows mean responses for different categories of private labels purchase preference (taken on a ranking scale of 1-4; where, 4 mean highest preferences and 1 mean lowest preference) with the corresponding standard deviations.

Table 4 : Category-Wise Private Label Purchase Preference

Statistic	Groceries	Food	Apparels	Toiletries
Mean	3.51	2.97	2.45	1.07
Std. Deviation	1.412	1.133	.702	1.170

It is interesting for this research that packaged food comes as second following only grocery products. According to the results, for grocery items around 38 % of respondents have given first preference to private label product and about 46% respondents prefer it as their second choice. Whereas for processed packaged food, the figures are 32% and 36% respectively. It is therefore possible to conclude that Groceries and Packaged food are the product category with high potentials for private label penetration. This is particularly true for the Indian market where the leading retailer is efficiently conducting the strategy of "differentiation prevention". Most of the processed food items under the private labels are similar to the products sold under the manufacturer brands. As far as the apparels are concerned that is another popular category with almost 30% of respondents giving first preference and around 13% have given second preference. Probably the reason for this may be that the younger group which didn't show preference to purchase grocery or food items take interest in purchasing it. Toiletries as a group shows poor penetration in the region as none have given first preference to it and only 5% respondent giving second preference.

It was also attempted to discover whether the propensity to buy private labels is associated with demographic or socio-economic characteristics of consumers.

It was found that the female consumers prefer to purchase private label more regularly in comparison to male consumers. Probably the reason may be that the females are more Price conscious then the male consumers in India and private labels are available at a little lower price in comparison to national brands. 39% females reported as regular and frequent buyer of private label in comparison to 24% male consumers.

Table 5 : Gender Store Brand Purchase Relation

Gender	Store Brand Purchase (in percent)				
	Regularly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Total
Male	22.0	11.9	10.2	1.7	45.8
Female	22.9	16.1	13.6	1.7	54.2
Total	44.9	28.0	23.7	3.4	100.0

However it has been observed that age and education were not significantly related to the reported frequency of private label purchase. This is in accordance with previous researches which also find rather weak association of propensity to buy private label and demographic characteristics of consumers (for review see: Baltas, 1997). Self-reported household disposable income has shown statistically significant effect on private label purchase frequency ($p=0.01$). Respondents in lower income groups are more frequent buyers of private label food products.

Table 6 : Impact of Disposable Income on the Frequency of Private Label Purchase

Income Group	Frequency of Private Label Purchase (in percent)				Total
	Regularly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	
< 2 Lac	17.6	14.4	15.3	2.5	49.8
2-4 Lac	14.7	7.6	4.2	.8	27.4
4-6 Lac	10.9	5.1	6.8	0	22.7
Total	43.2	27.1	26.3	3.4	100.0

($p = 0.01$; $n = 118$)

Also the size of a household is found (Family Structure) to be significantly related to private label product purchase frequency ($p=0.040$). However the medium size households comprising husband, wife and children reported maximum purchases. Large size households reported second and bachelors (Smaller households) reported rather week inclination towards purchase of private label products.

Table 7 : Impact of Household Size on the Frequency of Private Label Purchase

Family Structure	Frequency of Private Label Purchase				Total
	Regularly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	
Bachelor	7.6%	2.4%	15.3%	2.5%	27.8%
Husband, Wife & Children	19.5%	12.7%	7.6%	.8%	40.7%
Extended Family	16.1%	12.0%	3.4%	0%	31.5%
Total	43.2%	27.1%	26.3%	3.4%	100.0%

($p = 0.040$; $n = 118$)

The results from the consumer evaluation of potato chips are presented in the Tab. 8 which shows mean liking scores for three samples in two experimental conditions. The highest liking mean score in both experimental conditions has been given to the sample A which is the high quality product of the national market leader positioned in the premium segment. This manufacturer is also known for its long standing in market as a quality food product manufacturer and aggressive marketing strategies. The mean liking score for this sample increased significantly ($p=0.000$) when respondents knew the brand of the sample (in case of informed testing) then what it was in case of blind testing. Actually, the informed-blind mean ranking difference was the largest for this sample. In this case we can confirm an assimilation effect due to a positive image of the brand.

Table 8 : Mean Liking Scores of Hedonic Sensory Evaluation and Effect of Information about Brand

Sample Code	Mean Liking Score		Standard deviation		Mean Difference	Significance (2-tailed)
	Blind	Informed	Blind	Informed		
A	6.98	7.64	1.172	.485	.66	.000
B	6.53	7.08	.676	.451	.55	.002
C	4.27	4.28	.578	.586	.01	.932

The second ranked sample in blind testing was B which is a high quality private label owned by one of the largest and oldest organized retailer in India with

aggressive private label marketing strategy. In this case also the information about brand and origin in informed testing resulted in a higher mean ranking ($p=0.002$). It signifies that, when informed people ranked it high. Though, it is not as high as the national brand. The reason for giving higher ranking could be the reputation enjoyed by the large and old organized retailer.

Very close mean liking score has been given to Sample C which is a local label available as a generic product. In this case both average liking scores (Blind and informed) were lowest and information about the brand was not found to have a significant effect on likings of the consumers. The quality of this product obviously does not correspond to the expectations of Indian consumers. The brand has also lost image of reliable quality in the segment of processed food. For this sample there was no considerable difference in means in blind and informed testing. Thus, respondents in the study attested as rather reliable sensory evaluations.

CONCLUSION

The study confirms that the information about brand can significantly affect consumers' hedonic sensory judgment of food products. Consumer sensory judgment is therefore influenced by past experiences, familiarity with the product and retailer, advertising etc. and preference is therefore influenced by more than the taste of food itself. When comparing the impact of experimental condition with respect to the type of brand, strong effect of assimilation was observed in case of national labels. Impact of assimilation was also found in the case of private label products. It has been noticed that consumers have a set of expectation related to a certain private label which is furthermore influenced by the perceived image of the retailer. In case where the retailer has a good reputation assimilation has been positive. It might be therefore inferred that consumers when making sensory evaluation are influenced similarly by the private label and producer label. In other words there is no difference in consumer preferences regarding the type of label except in case of local labels. These findings contribute to complex matter and have important implications for strategic brand management. Consumers do not perceive private labels as a "second class" label, also in the case when the segment is non-diversified and only first generation private labels exist. Indian private label shoppers might be identified as a price-cautious but quality-sensitive. This can be inferred from the results of Sample C which is a local label. This highlights the necessity of permanent low price strategy for private label food and preventing differentiation from the producer brands in respect of perceived quality. On the other hand extrinsic cues of the products must be strengthened. This situation means that product and brand managers must begin to understand what drives the growing share of store brands.

Potential for competitive advantage for producer brands or manufacturer labels therefore relies on superior quality and highly differentiated images via advertising, effective and continuous product innovation and creative design. National brand producers need to put the emphasis on strategies that sustain and justify the price premium over private labeled goods.

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